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THE CONCEPT OF TIME IN SPRING SONATA BY ČIURLIONIS

The article deals with the pictorial sonata of Čiurlionis spring from the point of view of the category of space-time. The events of the sonata develop on the subtle plane of being, so it is logical that they are not tied to a specific moment, but take place in eternity. The concept is quite in the spirit of Russian symbolism, which also gravitates towards eternity.

Keywords: M. K. Čiurlionis, Spring sonata, space-time, questions “where and when”, “there and always”, eternal return, meaninglessness of existence, mythopoetical space-time, stroboscopic effect, invisible plane of being, symbol, eternity.

Sonata is a subjective lyrical and philosophical understanding of the concept of relationship between the man and the world. This is a lyrical monologue of the artist, conveying the whole spectrum of his impressions, inspired by an event or spectacle. In this case, let's talk about the phenomenon of spring. Of how it first appears on the subtle plane, how it flies in the air, driven by all winds, in order to finally find an earthly embodiment. And everything around – trees, birds, fish, people – obeys the crazy rhythm of spring.

So, Čiurlionis's Spring Sonata begins as a dramatic collision of two principles, like any spring, which crushes cold and ice with its powerful pressure.

Then astonished calm follows andante at a slowing pace, until it is completely frozen. And it is very strange that scherzo takes place in the under-water world. Scherzo better fits for the finale, which takes us back to the realm of cosmic existence. There, at a sky-high altitude, multicolored flags are unexpectedly frivolous, like linen in the wind. The overall light, joyful flavor would better correspond with the naughty scherzo.

But where, in what worlds, and when does the phenomenon of spring occur?

Spring ripens in cosmos and goes down to the earth from there. Spring is the eternal wind that bends the trees and turns the blades of the mill. Andante answers the questions arisen: where and when. Of course, everything happens “there and always”. It is the eternal work of turning the world around and grinding our hopes,

M. K. Čiurlionis. *Allegro (Sonata II)*. From cycle *Sonata II (Sonata of the Spring)*. 1907. Tempera on paper

aspirations and sorrows into flour. The flour will snow next winter, but will melt again with the next allegro of spring. It's the pagan attitude of time concentrated on itself, the cycle of absolutely everything and a return to heavenly source.

The sparsely populated, timber-yard region, where Druskininkai is located, mainly remained a pagan land at the beginning of the twentieth century. Later, although Catholicism strengthened its positions there, superstitions were widely spread among local dwellers, and the Lithuanians were considered pagans and sorcerers.

However, "there and always" proclaimed by Čiurlionis is not just a pagan sway of eternity, but also an eternal return, which artists of the turn of the century were concerned.

In the Spring Sonata individual being is not even considered, it most likely reveals the absolute being of nature not tied to a specific time. It affirms the value and solidity of every moment of life, as something everlasting.

Many creators of the Silver Age were obsessed with the Nietzsche's idea of eternal return. First of all, we are talking about the Russian symbolism. However, in most cases, poets familiar with Zarathustra realize only certain aspects of the idea of eternal return. For example, in the Alexander Blok's works a nihilistic motive prevails in the best traditions of decadence. Let's recall a well-known poem: "Night, street, lamp, drugstore." (БЛОК 2001: 171)

Night, street, lamp, drugstore,
A dull and meaningless light.
Go on and live another quarter century –
Nothing will change. There's no way out.

You'll die, then start from the beginning,
It will repeat, just like before:
Night, icy ripples on a canal,
Drugstore, street, lamp.

(Translated by *D. Belyayeva*)

Blok's life-affirming moment is reduced and darkened.

Indeed, the cosmological aspect of the idea of eternal return declares the complete meaninglessness of existence: if everything returns to normal in the end and there is nothing new under the sun, then existence has no meaning. As a result, nothing is achieved, nothing is redeemed, everything remains the same in eternity.

Discussing the idea of a return with a dwarf, Zarathustra asks the following questions: "Shouldn't everything that can go already has passed this path once? Shouldn't everything that can happen, have already happened once?" And then he asks: "Are things so firmly connected that this moment entails everything to come? Hence – also itself? For all that can go – shouldn't it once again go this long way forward!"

However, there is still a will to live. The anthropological aspect gives a “new center of gravity” to the existence, which is resolved in the imperative: live as if you wish yourself an endless repetition of every moment of your life. And this means: look, listen, breathe, drink spring with every cell of your body. If Blok, followed by Nietzsche, insists on the emptiness and meaninglessness of being, Čiurlionis endows existence with a new comprehensive meaning, namely, an endless renewal of life, to be exact. Spring is coming! It’s spring – and everything repeats again and again: love and joy, and the delight of being.

It should be emphasized that this cycle was written in 1907, when Čiurlionis experienced a huge uplift and long-awaited recognition. In a few years, Petersburg would infect and kill him with its depression, just as it would later kill Blok, who did not want to live on.

But of that time, back in 1907, the myth of the eternal return was imagined by Čiurlionis as an optimistic perspective: the artist, as a strong and exceptional person, looked forward to the Övermensch, therefore, any return promised to the artist a repetition of creative acts and rapture at every moment of his own being. The open universe gave him endless chances to transform and grow above himself. Although Friedrich Nietzsche more than once emphasized that the universe is indifferent to human existence, but a person can still rely on the world around and draw strength in each new spring.

Mythopoetical space-time of the Spring Sonata unfolds on three levels: the blades of the universal mill, or its super-idea, which, consolidating on the earth plane, breaks down into many objects no larger than a beetle – these mills are seen from the cosmic height in such away. The main figurative motive – the motive of the mill’s wings against the background of the open sky stands out like a leitmotif in music, and the accompanying motives are the hills, running towards the horizon, and the stars, which are comparable with the development of the “side theme” of the sonata.

The movement of the mill’s blades creates the so-called stroboscopic effect, or the appearance of natural movement. The mills on the hillside in the Spring Sonata are fractal. The One disintegrates into many similarities of its own, a similar technique will later be used in the “analytical art” of the Russian avant-garde artist Pavel Filonov, when a separate detail carries the stylistics of the whole work.

M. K. Čiurlionis. *Andante (Sonata II)*. From cycle *Sonata II (Sonata of the Spring)*. 1907. Tempera on paper

Andante is an absolutely symmetrical work (even the clouds – lightened abstract spots, which repeat the main theme of the first part by their outlines – are deliberately symmetrical) the illusion of the whirling motion of the blades gives the cyclical nature to time, and the feelings become quite and harmonious.

The Russian icon is also symmetrical, which depicts not the earthly, but a subtle, invisible plane of being, the space of eternity, where the events of celestial history endlessly take place. Čiurlionis literally paints the heavens, what Russian icon painters did too. Their art of depicting the invisible layer of being was rediscovered at the turn of the century and was welcomed by the Symbolists and later by the Avant-gardists.

The key word of the Symbolists is eternity according to Feodor Sologub. The symbol is a window to eternity. Eternity is a continuous transmission of

M. K. Čiurlionis. *Scherzo (Sonata II)*. From cycle *Sonata II (Sonata of the Spring)*. 1907. Tempera on paper

the Platonic idea that exists on the subtle plane. Therefore, the main principle of symbolism may be designated as double-world, or the simultaneous deployment of events on the subtle and earthly planes of being.

The events in all four paintings of the Spring Sonata cycle take place not only simultaneously, but in the space of eternity, just like the events of the traditional Russian icon.

It is known that Čiurlionis admired the Russian culture. It is not surprising that his Spring Sonata is consonant with the vision of Pushkin's prophet (Пушкин 1983: 145):

I heard the shudders of the sky,
The sweep of angel hosts on high,

M. K. Čiurlionis. *Finale (Sonata IV)*. From cycle *Sonata II (Sonata of the Spring)*. 1907. Tempera on paper

The creep of beasts below in the seas,
The seep of sap in valley trees.
(Translated by A. Z. Foreman)

Pushkin's prophet, like Čiurlionis, traveled up and down the world tree. Both artists imagined the underworld as an underwater kingdom. But why is the underwater world a scherzo, when fish move slowly, like in a dream, skillfully bending around the fishing nets? Fish do not go to traps, and in this they are certainly right. Fish, unlike people, know the deceptive essence of spring. It's arrival promises a lot every time, and as a result betrays, any new hope turns out to be fruitless. And everything that was once created by human hands rests at the bottom in the form of meaningless ruins. The deep sea has nothing to do with a human being.

Fish in general is a polysemantic symbol, saturated with mystical content, but not only. At the beginning of the twentieth century, fish, among other things, certainly sent us to the dark ocean of the unconsciousness, about which Freud wrote so much. Fish is a symbol of libido, moreover, apparently, a symbol of the revival of libido. In later works, Freud expanded the concept of libido and saw in it not only sexual, vital energy, the energy of the life instinct. In spring sexual psychosis, aimed at reviving life in all its manifestations invariably embrace all living things.

In music, the scherzo also demonstrates various shades of humor, playful intonation, in which one can just tell about the danger of love adventures, insidious nets that wait innocent lovers while plunging into the dark abyss of passion. Many go to the bottom, not everyone experiences the soaring of spirit at transcendental height, where the spring wind carries playful multi-colored flags as a symbol of worldly joy.

This is how the final is born in a strange combination of cosmic design and playful flags. But this is exactly how it is. Our simple joy and misfortune sooner or later are carried away into the clouds, and the cosmic wind scatters them without a trace. It has always been and will be this way, everything will be repeated in the new spring – if not with us, then with someone else. And what is our suffering against the backdrop of eternity?

Artistic creativity, along with a myth, is one of the sources of reflection of eternal return. Creativity is not aimed at formulating judgments, which demands a logical basis and evidence. This is precisely the advantage of creativity over philosophy. So we can confirm that the events of the Spring Sonata take place “there and always”.

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LAIKO SAMPRATA ČIURLIONIO
PAVASARIO SONATOJE

Santrauka

Straipsnyje vaizdinė Čiurlionio pavasario sonata nagrinėjama erdvėlaikio kategorijos požiūriu. Sonatos įvykiai vystosi subtiliojoje būties plotmėje, todėl logiška, kad jie nėra susieti su konkrečia akimirka, o vyksta amžinybėje. Konceptija yra gana rusiškos simbolikos dvasia, kuri taip pat traukia į amžinybę.

Raktažodžiai: M. K. Čiurlionis, Pavasario sonata, erdvė-laikas, klausimai „kur ir kada“, „ten ir visada“, amžinas sugrįžimas, egzistencijos beprasmybė, mitopoetinė erdvė-laikas, stroboskopinis efektas, nematoma būties plotmė, simbolis, amžinybė.